

Title

Final Report to the US Forest Service by the University of California at Berkeley

Project

Assessment of Stand Stress and Genetic Response to Aspen Management

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Project partners

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Project Goals

Motivation

Forest management resources are often limited, so actions are often selected based on the characteristics of locations ('prioritization'). Taking such actions requires knowledge of which areas are undergoing change. Additionally, for locations that have been actively managed, it can be important to assess the response of the land to the action ('monitoring'). Common characteristics to assess may include mortality or regeneration. However, in all cases, obtaining relevant data can be challenging. Ground-based field measurements can be costly, or logistically infeasible in many locations, especially those far from roads. Airborne measurements with expert human surveyors can enable spatial upscaling, but spatial resolution is typically low (+/- 100-200 m) and inferences are limited by what is visible to the human eye at the time of flight.

An alternative decision-support tool could leverage remotely-sensed satellite imagery, which would provide spatially extensive coverage and regular updates over time without the costs and challenges of fieldwork. Instruments such as Landsat's Thematic Mapper and Sentinel-2's Multi-Spectral Imager provide coverage of multiple visible and shortwave infrared spectral bands with pixel sizes of 10-60 meters and revisit rates of ~10 days. These spectral bands potentially contain information about the characteristics of Earth surface vegetation, and therefore could be leveraged for trend assessments and then decision-support.

One commonly-used approach with remotely-sensed imagery is to train machine learning models that leverage spectral features to predict vegetation features, e.g. forest mortality. However, this approach requires substantial training datasets (i.e. ground-truth validations of vegetation showing and not showing mortality) that may not always be available. Moreover, separate training datasets are usually required for each vegetation type / species (due to their different spectral properties), further increasing the effective field dataset workload.

An alternative approach that does not require training machine learning algorithms is to rely on spectral indices that have known physiological linkages and that have been shown in prior studies to be associated with relevant vegetation change. Two key indices are (Gao, 1996):

- Normalized difference vegetation index (**NDVI**) - defined as $(NIR - RED)/(NIR + RED)$ where NIR reflects a near-infrared spectral band and RED indicates a visible (red) spectral band. Values range from -1 to +1, with more negative values corresponding to water/rock and more positive values corresponding to vegetation. Increases in NDVI for vegetation are typically associated with increased canopy growth or closure, or increased photosynthetic activity within a canopy.
- Normalized difference moisture index (NDMI) - defined as $(NIR - SWIR)/(NIR + SWIR)$ where SWIR indicates a shortwave infrared spectral band. Values range from -1 to +1, with more negative values corresponding to bare soil or rock or stressed vegetation and more positive values corresponding to dense or unstressed vegetation.

Numerous prior studies have used either NDVI or NDMI to track changes in vegetation composition and stress over time (Brodrick & Asner, 2017; Hais et al., 2019; Lastovicka et al., 2020; Le et al., 2023). Reasonable hypotheses to consider are that:

- Mortality is associated with decreases in NDVI or NDMI;
- Regrowth is associated with increases in NDVI or NDMI;
- Stress and incipient mortality are associated with decreases in NDVI or NDMI.

These hypotheses are potentially valid across vegetation types; while the absolute magnitude of NDVI and NDMI in any given location may differ (e.g., conifer forest vs. sagebrush shrubland vs riparian meadow), the directionality of trends is potentially consistent across locations experiencing the same dynamics.

This project therefore aims to assess the value of mapping NDMI and NDVI trends for the Grand Mesa, Uncompahgre and Gunnison (GMUG) National Forests in Colorado. The project focused on providing assessments for the South Uncompahgre Hazardous Fuels and Ecological Resiliency (SUHFER) project, which covers the Norwood and Ouray Districts of the Uncompahgre National Forest, but was later extended to cover all GMUG National Forests. This landscape includes a diversity of vegetation types including aspen forests, conifer forests of various compositions, Gambel oak thickets, sagebrush steppe, and grasslands. The University of California at Berkeley was invited to develop remote sensing data products, web applications, and field validations for decision-support in this region.

Results from this work are potentially valuable for:

- Providing an immediate decision-support toolkit in the SUHFER project region
- Assessing the reliability and value of NDVI and NDMI-based data products
- Building National Forest partner experience/comfort engaging with satellite remote sensing and web application tools

Questions

(1) Are ground-based forest mortality/regrowth dataset trends congruent with satellite-derived trends in the study region?

(2) What are the spatial and temporal trends in satellite-derived moisture (NDMI) and greenness (NDVI) indices in the study region?

Methods

Study area

This project covered the entirety of the Grand Mesa, Uncompahgre, and Gunnison (GMUG) National Forests (NF).

Satellite imagery preparation

We first collected and prepared multispectral satellite imagery covering the entirety of the study area over the years 2018-2024. We extracted all available Level-2A surface reflectance data

from the Sentinel-2 multispectral satellite series for the snow-free growing months (July - September) for each year. Imagery from this series covers 440-2200 nm with a band-dependent spectral and spatial resolution of 13-184 nm and 10-60 m, respectively, and has a revisit time of ~5 days. Of the publicly-available satellite surface reflectance datasets with regular repeat coverage of the study area, Sentinel-2 has the highest spatial resolution and the best coverage of the red edge wavelengths (~700-800 nm) which are key for monitoring vegetation health.

We summarized all available images for a given month to a single mosaic. To do so, we used all available images for a given month to generate a greenest- and least-cloudy pixel mosaic covering the entire study area. We calculated greenness as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and derived cloud coverage from the Sentinel Scene Classification (SCL) algorithm (Main-Knorn et al., 2017), and then selected the greenest and least cloudy value available for each pixel from the time series. We excluded the three atmospheric bands (Band 1, Band 9, Band 10) from our analysis and disaggregated the remaining bands to 10 m spatial resolution to enable stacking different bands for statistical analyses.

We then used the resulting monthly best-pixel mosaics to calculate two spectral indices: the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI). We used bands 3, 8, and 11 from the Sentinel-2 imagery to represent red, near infrared, and shortwave infrared wavelengths, respectively. This resulted in a time series of observations for each spectral index at 10 m spatial resolution, covering the entire GMUG for the growing season months July - September and the years 2018-2024 (Figure 1).

Modeling changes in canopy spectra over time

We then used the resulting NDVI and NDMI time series to model the spectral trajectory of each pixel within the study area. For each pixel, we trained an independent linear regression model to predict each spectral index as a function of decimal-time. The slope of each linear regression model thus represented the modeled change in the spectral index per year. A positive slope value indicates that the spectral index is increasing (that the polygon is getting greener or more densely vegetated, in the case of NDVI), while a negative slope value indicates that the spectral index is decreasing (getting drier or less densely vegetated, in the case of NDMI).

We also summarized these trends for each FSveg stand polygon intersecting the study area (Figure 2). The version of FSveg used for this analysis was dated from February 2, 2021. For each stand polygon, we took the same modeling approach described above using the mean of all pixel values contained within the polygon at each time step. We also calculated a p-value for each stand polygon regression model to assess the significance of the modeled relationship. A p-value represents a statistical test of the null hypothesis that there is no linear relationship between the predictor and response variables. A high p-value indicates a failure to reject the null hypothesis, while a low p-value indicates a statistically significant linear relationship. A common threshold p-value to indicate statistical significance is 0.05.

Comparison with ground-based trends

We then collected a variety of pre-existing ground-based observations of changes in forest stand stress over time from USFS and external partners to assess the congruence with the satellite-derived trends. We were able to access three datasets from the USFS Forest Health

Program (FHP), Uncompahgre Plateau Collaborative Forest Landscape Restoration Program (UP-CFLRP), and Spruce Beetle Epidemic and Aspen Decline Management Response (SBEADMR) program. Ground-based plots from all three programs were located within the GMUG and were visited at multiple time points. Preprocessing and analysis of each dataset is described below.

USFS FHP Sudden Aspen Decline (SAD) monitoring

Data from the USFS FHP Sudden Aspen Decline (SAD) monitoring project included 81 paired healthy and SAD plots (Figure 3). Each plot was visited three times: once from 2007-2008, in 2013, and again from 2020-2022. All plots were metric variable radius plots, ranging from a basal area factor (BAF) of 1-3. The BAF was based on the original stand density, measuring at least 10 aspen trees at each plot. The majority of trees surveyed within and across plots were quaking aspen (*Populus tremuloides*). At each plot visit, the field team recorded the total number of trees surveyed and the number of those trees which were healthy, dead, and declining. We used these values to calculate five stand stress metrics: the percentage of healthy, live, dead, declining, and dead or declining trees at each plot, at each time point. Because the plots had a variable radius with a fixed BAF, these stem-based percentages were proportional to basal area.

We then extracted the full time series of spectral data to each plot center coordinate. Given that the pixel-size of the spectral data was 10 m, we assumed that each plot was contained entirely within the single pixel containing the center coordinates.

UP-CFLRP

Data from the UP-CFLRP included 49 plots which were visited between two and four times between 2014-2023 (Figure 3). Plots were 164 x 164 ft squares (~50 x 50 m) and included a wide variety of tree species (e.g. POTR, PIPO, ABLA, PSME, PIEN, PIPU, QUGA). At each plot visit, the field team recorded the DBH and status (standing live, standing dead, down live, down dead, stump) of each tree. We used these values to calculate three stand stress metrics: the basal area density of standing live, standing dead, and dead or down trees at each plot, at each time point.

We then extracted the full time series of spectral data to each plot. Because the plots (50 m) were larger than the pixel-size of the spectral data (10 m), we generated a 50 m square around each plot center coordinate and extracted all pixel values where the pixel fell mostly within the square. We summarized the extracted pixel values for each plot as the minimum, maximum, and mean of each spectral index.

SBEADMR

Data from the SBEADMR included 53 plots which were visited either two or three times between 2015-2023 (Figure 3). Plots were 0.05 ha (~25 m) and included a wide variety of tree species (e.g. PIEN, POTR, ABLA, PIAR, PICO, PSME). For each plot visit, the data were summarized according to the total basal area of each combination of species, status (live or dead), and size class (sapling, pole, saw timber). We used these values to calculate two stand stress metrics:

the percentage of total basal area represented by live and dead trees at each time plot and time point.

We then extracted the full time series of spectral data to each plot center coordinate. We assumed that each plot was spectrally represented by the single pixel containing the center coordinates.

Correlation between *in situ* and spectral trajectories

For each dataset, for each plot, and for each stand stress metric, we trained a linear regression model to predict the stand stress metric as a function of time. We then trained a second set of models for each dataset, plot, and spectral index to predict the spectral index as a function of time. Next, to assess the congruence between the ground-based stand stress and satellite-derived spectral trajectories for each dataset, we extracted the modeled slope coefficient for each linear regression model for each plot. We then generated a correlation matrix to assess the correlation, across all plots, between the slope of each ground-based stand stress metric and spectral index model for each dataset.

Results / data products

We developed a monthly growing season time series of NDVI and NDMI covering the entire study area at 10 m resolution from 2018-2024 (Figure 1). We then modeled the change over time in satellite-derived moisture (NDMI) and greenness (NDVI) indices for each 10 m pixel and each FSveg stand polygon contained within the study area (Figure 2).

Question 1: Correlation between ground-based and spectral trends

We modeled the temporal trends in ground-based stand stress metrics and satellite-derived greenness and moisture indices for each plot across all three external datasets (Figure 4). We then created a correlation matrix for each dataset to assess congruence between all available ground-based and satellite-derived metrics (Figure 5).

For the USFS FHP dataset, the temporal trends in both NDVI and NDMI were significantly correlated in the expected direction with temporal trends in all but one of the ground-based stand stress metrics (Figure 5ai). The satellite-derived greenness and wetness trends were positively correlated with the ground-measured trend in the percentage of trees that were healthy and the percentage of trees that were alive, and negatively correlated with the ground-measured trend in the percentage of trees that were dead and the percentage of trees that were dead or declining. The satellite-derived metrics were not significantly correlated with the ground-measured trend in the percentage of trees that were declining. These results suggest a strong congruence between the satellite-derived metrics and the ground-based stand stress metrics. These relationships retained the same direction and significance when subset to healthy and SAD plots (Figure 5aii).

In the UP-CFLRP dataset, the temporal trend in polygon mean NDMI was strongly, significantly correlated with the temporal trends in the ground-based metrics in the directions that we would expect (Figure 5bi). The temporal trend in standing live basal area density was most strongly correlated with the trend in mean NDMI within the plot polygons (Pearson's

correlation coefficient = 0.70; p-value = 0.00), and only slightly less strongly correlated with minimum and maximum NDMI within plot polygons. Relationships between spectral and ground-based trajectories were stronger when dead and down trees were combined into a single category (Figure 5bi). The NDVI trends showed weaker, marginally significant to non-significant correlations with all ground-based metrics in the expected directions.

In the SBEADMR dataset, the temporal trend in NDMI was significantly correlated with the temporal trends in both ground-based metrics of stand stress in the direction that we would expect (Figure 5ci). The temporal trend in NDVI showed the opposite direction of correlation that we would expect with both ground metrics, but the relationships were weak and not statistically significant. These relationships retained the same direction and significance when subset to treatment and control plots (Figure 5a_{ii}).

Question 2: Spatial and temporal trends in satellite-derived moisture and greenness indices

Heterogeneity in landscape-scale patterns was evident (Figure 2). NDMI and NDVI trends were strongly correlated with each other, but the strength and nature of the correlation depended on the vegetation type (Figure 6). Spruce/fir displayed the greatest deviation from a 1:1 relationship, indicating that decrease in NDMI led to smaller decreases in NDVI. Additionally, the overall strength of correlation was weakest for spruce-fir and aspen-conifer indicating that NDVI and NDMI trends were relatively decoupled in these cover types only (i.e. drying without browning, or vice versa).

Across vegetation types, the distribution of trends in NDVI and NDMI were heterogeneous (Figure 7). When not considering statistical significance, the median trend was slightly positive for most vegetation types, but with substantial spread towards negative and positive values. A positive trend can indicate a recovery process but not necessarily recovery; a strict interpretation would be 'doing less badly than before'.

When grouping trends by statistical significance and accounting for land area, each vegetation type showed a range of significantly negative, significantly positive, and non-significant changes over time (Figure 8). The most frequent significantly negative trends were found for spruce-fir, lodgepole pine, cool-moist mixed conifer, and aspen-conifer NDVI and NDMI. Thus, stability is most common for each vegetation type, but there are also regions of significant increase and decrease for each vegetation type..

Despite these vegetation-specific differences, there was no clear differentiation of temporal trend slopes by elevation or cosine aspect for either NDVI or NDMI (Figure 9).

Google Earth Engine application

We developed a prototype Google Earth Engine (GEE) application to share the spatial datasets developed in this project in a code-free and interactive environment. This application displays the full spectral time series and modeled spectral trajectory for each pixel and FSveg polygon in the study area. Users can visualize NDVI or NDMI trends at the pixel and polygon-level, and

can filter polygons by cover type and significance. Users can also visualize polygons describing the extent of known fire and timber harvests that occurred within the GMUG during the years 2018-2024, for comparison with the modeled spectral trends.

Discussion

Question 1

The project was limited by the scarcity of available and harmonizable field observations of mortality or regrowth that were coincident with the satellite data products. For the datasets that were available, there was reasonable congruence between the field observations and the satellite-derived metrics, i.e. locations where if one dataset indicated mortality, the other also would, and similarly for regeneration. Across all three datasets, there was a significant correlation between spectral and ground-based trajectories in the expected direction of 0.3-0.70 (Figure 5). The congruence across datasets is notable given the varying plot characteristics (e.g. size, species present) and field measurement approaches.

Ground-based stress metrics showed a stronger correlation with NDMI than with NDVI values. This may be in part due to the known tendency of NDVI to saturate at higher levels of greenness or vegetation density. Satellite-derived trends were better able to capture large changes in ground-based measures of forest health (e.g. severe mortality events) than subtle ones (e.g. canopy health decline).

Based on visual assessment of the data product, and conversations with GMUG staff, our overall assessment is that the metrics provide valuable information for decision-support. While the level of congruence is not sufficiently high to confidently replace field datasets, it is high enough to recommend usage for areas where no other datasets are available. That is, the data products are likely valuable for providing triage and initial assessment of remote or unstudied sites, enabling limited resources to be more efficiently allocated to further field work.

Question 2

The project identified extensive spatial variation in greenness (NDVI) and moisture (NDMI) trends across the GMUG National Forests. Some areas showed no statistically significant trend in either metrics, while many showed significant trends. Some vegetation types, especially firs and spruces, showed the most substantial declines in both NDVI and NDMI, but this effect did not seem to be mediated by topography. Additionally, the decoupling of NDMI and NDVI in certain vegetation types such as spruce/fir indicates that these metrics can potentially reflect independent processes of canopy greening vs. canopy stress, which may be particularly useful when considering future work to develop early-warning indicators.

Limitations

The availability of field observations posed a key limit to model validation. Even where available, the time period of many field observations did not always match spectral time series well, as much of the field data observations began pre-2010, while Sentinel-2 satellite imagery only became available in 2017. Additionally, the spatial coverage of the field observations was

primarily limited to locations close to roads and on non-steep slopes, leading to bias in the congruence assessments of satellite and field observations.

Changes in spectral indices at each pixel were summarized using linear regressions of index vs. time. This approach provides an easily comparable metric (slope, p-value) but necessarily obscures non-linear variation within each pixel. Step-changes, accelerating/decelerating relationships, and temporary spikes in spectral indices are not detected via this approach. Similarly, within-season trends are ignored in favor of summarizing annual trends. The underlying workflow preserves the raw data so such analyses could be carried out if later of interest.

Due to the large size of the pixels, it is not possible to determine that within-pixel changes are driven by a demographic process (e.g., mortality, regrowth) affecting a single species, or all the species in this pixel. Spectral index changes actually could be driven by species turnover, shifts in relative abundance, or a complex mix of regrowth and mortality among species. The grouping of pixels into FSveg polygons reduces the magnitude of these effects, but finer-scale and species-level inference is not formally possible.

The spectral indices are also sensitive only to the properties of the canopy, and as such provide a limited view of the underlying demographic processes. For example, temporary canopy defoliation (causing reduced NDVI) may not actually reflect mortality; similarly, increased NDMI may reflect canopy closure more than stress reduction. Thus, only coarse inferences about forest dynamics should be made based on these metrics unless further field data are available.

Possible extensions

This study did not carry out time-series analyses to determine how spatiotemporally variable stressors (e.g., summer heatwaves, winter snowpacks, early-summer droughts) or treatments (e.g., coppicing, burning, grazing) shifted metrics. Such work would go beyond the scope of the linear trend analysis performed, but would be feasible and could be valuable for determining the consequences or time lags between stressor and stress response, or between management action and vegetation response (e.g., (Bigler et al., 2007; Kannenberg et al., 2020)).

These data products could also potentially be valuable for developing early-warning indicators of vegetation change, via incipient stress leading to later mortality (e.g., (Anderegg et al., 2019; Goulden & Bales, 2019; Rogers et al., 2018)). This project provides key datasets to support such work, but integration of other datasets and development of machine-learning algorithms would be necessary to yield advances.

Data / code availability

The resulting Google Earth Engine application can be found at:
<https://sufer.projects.earthengine.app/view/gmug-canopy-health>

All relevant code developed through this project can be found at:

<https://github.com/erin-carroll/SUHFER>

Final spatial data can be found at:

<https://usfs.box.com/s/yef72e9k5rheqlmegth1fim29xphxrlr>.

Spatial data include (1) annual rasters of NDMI and NDVI covering the study area at 10 m resolution (2018-2024), (2) the modeled change in NDMI and NDVI over the same period, summarized for each FSVeg polygon as the slope and the significance of the linear trend, and (3) the raw and processed ground-based observations of forest stand stress collected from USFS and external partners.

Questions and feedback

Erin Carroll was the lead developer of the algorithms and data products and should be the first point of contact with technical inquiries, at least through 2026. Broader questions about the project and extensions should be directed to Benjamin Blonder. In the event that Erin Carroll moves to another position, Benjamin Blonder can also address technical questions.

Figures

Figure 1.

NDMI and NDVI as calculated over a small example region in July, 2018.

Figure 2.

Examples of change in NDMI per year for multiple FSveg stand polygons.

Figure 3.

Locations of the ground-based stand stress monitoring plots from the USFS Forest Health Program (FHP), Uncompahgre Plateau Collaborative Forest Landscape Restoration Program (UP-CFLRP), and Spruce Beetle Epidemic and Aspen Decline Management Response (SBEADMR) program.

Figure 4.

Example plots from each dataset illustrating the congruence between the temporal trends in one ground-based metric of stand stress and the satellite-derived metrics of greenness (NDVI) and moisture (NDMI).

Figure 5.

Relationship between the temporal trends of each ground-based stand stress metric and each satellite-derived stress metric across all plots for each dataset. For **(A)** USFS FHP, **(B)** UP-CFLRP, and **(C)** SBEADMR datasets, subfigures **(i)** show correlation matrices for all plots. The value in the box indicates the pearson's correlation coefficient for the two variables. The value in the parentheses indicates the p-value of the correlation test for a null hypothesis of no correlation. Values are bolded if the p-value indicates a statistically significant correlation ($p < 0.05$). Subfigures **(ii)** visualize the relationship between the spectral and ground-based trends, divided by relevant grouping factors.

(A) USFS FHP

(i)

(ii)

(B) UP-CFLRP

(i)

(ii)

(C) SBEADMR

(i)

(ii)

Figure 6.

Correlation between temporal trend slopes of NDVI and NDMI. Points are colored based on whether the trend is statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. Each point represents a FSveg polygon and is sized by relative area.

Figure 7.

Distribution of temporal trend slopes for (A) NDVI and (B) NDMI. Boxplots do not show outliers and are not filtered by statistical significance. Each point represents a FSveg polygon.

(A)

(B)

Figure 8.

Distribution of temporal trend slopes for (A) NDVI and (B) NDMI, grouped by statistical significance. Each bar represents the summed area of all underlying FSveg polygons.

(A)

(B)

Figure 9.

Distribution of temporal trend slopes by elevation and cosine aspect (-1 = SW, S, SE; 0 = W, E; 1 = NW, N, NE) for (A) NDVI and (B) NDMI.

(A)

(B)

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